

LEADERSHIP STYLES AND TYPES

Jumaniyazova Dilbar Azatovna

NSPI named after Ajiniyaz faculty of Pedagogy Direction school management

Abstract: This type of leadership requires a high-level organization of the team, in which it should not interfere with any component of the team's work and should not disturb the interaction and relations of its members. Currently, the use of this method in the activities of enterprises gives positive results in working with employees

Key words: Leader, enterprise, manager, action.

A style is a system that is always used in leadership. The style is a way of realizing the leader's style adopted by a certain manager in accordance with his personal subjective - mental description.

Leadership style is a characteristic behavior of a manager. A more complete meaning of the leadership style: is the relative strict system ways, style and practical activity of the manager. In addition, the management style means the behavior and behavior of the manager in the process of preparation and implementation of management decisions.

It can be seen that the style is a unique individual reality, because it is determined by the specific characteristics of a concrete person and reflects his nature of working with people and decision-making technology. Leadership styles are divided into three types.

1. Authoritarian type of leadership. This type of leader takes full responsibility for the activities of his subordinates. He tries to pass all available information through himself. Limits direct communication between team members. He cannot bear to be criticized for his inappropriate actions. He likes to sharply criticize the actions

of his subordinates. Such leaders usually do not like to talk a lot, but when dealing with their subordinates, the height of their leadership pride and arrogance is noticeable. Usually, an authoritarian is in a frowning mood in front of his subordinates. However, the autocratic management method cannot be called bad in all respects. In some cases, due to the low cultural level and morals of the subordinate, choosing the autocratic management style may also work.

But when all-round democratic relations in the team mature, the leader is forced to change his work style. Thus, the leader's autocratic management style cannot be evaluated only negatively. Because it shows its positive side in a certain period of the history of the development of management relations.

2. Democratic type of leadership. In this type of leadership, the leader carries out his activities relying on the members of the team under his guidance. Responsibility for activity is distributed among subordinates. Along with encouraging the direct relations of the team members with each other, the leader listens to the opinion expressed by the employees, consults with them, takes into account their positive aspects, and rewards the advanced ones and other employees. This type of leadership develops personal initiative and creative activity of subordinates and creates a friendly and working atmosphere in the team. This not only affects the atmosphere in the team, but also has a direct positive effect on its work results.

This type of leadership requires a high-level organization of the team, in which he should not interfere with the work of any component of the team and not disrupt the interaction and relations of their members. Currently, the use of this method in the activities of enterprises gives positive results in working with employees.

3. Liberal type of leadership. It practically does not interfere with team activities, it gives employees complete independence regarding the opportunity to demonstrate individual and team creativity. Such a leader is tactful with subordinates and can

reverse decisions he has made before if they threaten his reputation. They are characterized by a lack of initiative and a feeling of not understanding the instructions of higher management bodies. In them, the request to influence the team, advice forms take the main place.

A liberal manager is afraid of conflict and works mainly in agreement with subordinates.

It is passive in performing control functions, it can be said that it works according to the flow. His gentle communication with people prevents him from gaining a real reputation, because some employees demand relief from him, and he does everything he can to avoid spoiling his relationship with them. In this way, the leader of the liberal style cannot reveal his clearly expressed abilities, pays little attention to the behavior of his subordinates, and controls with laxity, as a result of which his performance is ineffective.

It can be seen in practice that all factors are interrelated in leadership. Companies should implement a style that embodies the need for the boss to lead, and the employee to realize his individuality, because the person doing a certain job knows that job better than even the captain, so he is able to improve this job better than others. In this approach, the leader exercises leadership, but the worker knows his job well in a certain level of detail. This method is called "directive independence". Leadership should be at the top of the organization and it should try to create the right environment for the necessary improvement. Leaders of this type motivate, inspire, support, lead and inspire all employees of the organization.

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